

Design of an In-Lab Experimentation Rack System for the ACUTE Multi-Channel Tactile System

Elvar Atli Ævarsson
University of Iceland
eae19@hi.is

Mathias Damgård
University of Iceland
mld8@hi.is

Árni Kristjánsson
University of Iceland
ak@hi.is

Runar Unnthorsson
University of Iceland
runson@hi.is

ABSTRACT

Listening to music, as an ensemble of audible acoustic frequencies carefully organized over a time period, is an experience that can generate pleasure and enhance the mood but many take for granted. However, many people with cochlear implants (CI) describe the experience as not so pleasant as the implants alter the frequency perception. Using tactile feedback to aid the hard of hearing is a methodology that has been studied in recent years. Building on previous work from the H2020 funded Sound of Vision project (No: 643636), we propose to modify the tactile belt developed in that project by replacing the motors with voice coils in order to make it a better suitable tactile display for conveying musical features. The aim is to help the CI recipients to better enjoy music.

This paper will outline the ideology of the project as well as describe the in-lab system used for experimentation while designing the ACUTE Multi-Channel Tactile System (Multi-CaTS). With 64 channels of audio to drive the array of voice coils comprising the tactile display, the in-lab rack system will be used to design methods for mapping music to multi-channel tactile feedback.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cochlear implants can vastly improve the quality of life of people with severe hearing impairment. Being able to hear and understand speech is an untold luxury to people who have spent years or decades in silence. For the purpose of one-on-one communication in a quiet environment, the cochlear implant has shown great results. However, with more complex acoustic signals, such as music, the results can be disappointing as crucial musical elements like pitch and timbre are lost [1], which greatly affects the perception of melody, harmony and tone quality.

In the Sound of Vision (SoV) project, a cross-disciplinary research group developed a system for assisting visually impaired people with orientation and navigation [2–5]. The

Figure 1. The Sound of Vision Tactile Belt comprised of a 6×10 array of ERM motors.

tactile belt, shown in figure 1, is an important part of that system. Consisting of a 6×10 array of eccentric rotating mass vibration (ERM) motors forming a tactile display, the SoV Tactile Belt receives signals from a computer which maps images from a 3-D camera (worn on the subject's forehead) to localized vibrations on the tactile display, creating an image of potential obstructions in the near environment.

Our goal is to use the general idea of the SoV Tactile Belt to further increase the music enjoyment of cochlear implant users. In doing so, we modify the belt by replacing the ERM motors with specially designed voice coils. While ERM motors worked well in the SoV project, they have the disadvantage of working at a fixed frequency depending on operating voltage and load [2]. Any change in pressure applied on the motors by the body will thus have an effect on the vibrational frequency. Voice coils on the other hand directly react to audio signals. Substituting ERM motors with voice coils, driven by low-power audio amplifiers, will therefore greatly simplify the control of both vibrational frequency and amplitude.

Since the new tactile display will contain 60 voice coils, with each controlled individually, the system will need to include 60 independent audio channels with the required amplification for each coil. Making it a compact and portable system will be a challenging task. The first step will however be to design and build a proof-of-concept system that can be used for lab experiments where the use of voice coils will be compared to the old SoV Tactile Belt, where

Figure 2. Diagram of the cochlear implant. Electrodes surgically implanted inside the cochlea receive information of stimulation level and directly trigger the auditory nerves. [6]

different audio-tactile mapping techniques will be compared, etc. This paper describes the hardware system setup for this work and further development.

2. COCHLEAR IMPLANTS

The basic structure of a human ear with a cochlear implant can be seen in figure 2. A microphone placed by the outer ear picks up acoustic signals which a processor then analyzes in terms of frequency and amplitude and divides into frequency bands, with each band assigned to a single electrode in an array of electrodes surgically implanted in the cochlea. A transmitter sends radio signals containing information on the stimulation level assigned to each electrode. The electrodes then activate the hair cells similarly positioned in the cochlea, thus directly triggering the auditory nerves and enabling the person to hear.

Since the number of hair cells in the inner ear is in tens of thousands, implanting one electrode per hair cell for a full resolution is impossible. Instead space limitation restricts the number of electrodes down to 16-22 (depending on the manufacturer), thus greatly affecting the precision of sound. This heavily distorts the perception of music.

2.1 Cross-modal plasticity in CI users

The brain has a way of adapting to sensory loss. With one sense lost, the area of the brain devoted to that sense gets a new role dedicated to other senses. For example, blind people tend to learn how to use auditory cues to a greater effect. The above mentioned SoV project showed good results in using the tactile belt as pathway between the somatosensory and visual systems.

Recent studies show that children with CI are generally susceptible to cross-modal reorganization between the somatosensory and auditory systems for speech recognition [7]. Furthermore, music has been presented to the deaf and hard of hearing using tactile displays, for example in form of the Model Human Cochlea [8] with a 2×8 array of voice coils arranged in the back of a chair. However, al-

most all tactile solutions have been low resolution tactile devices [8–10]. In this project we are developing a high-resolution tactile display (60 actuators) with actuators that cover a wide frequency range (see section 3.4).

With this project, our goal is to design a system that can in some way replace the musical elements lost to CI users, by means of localized vibration patterns applied alongside music signals.

2.2 Experimenting with audio-tactile mappings for musical pleasure

There are many issues to consider when expressing music using tactile stimulation. Mapping will play an integral part in the overall experience, as it ultimately determines the way the music is perceived by the CI user. Two types of audio-tactile mappings have been proposed and are currently being tested in our initial study using the SoV Tactile Belt with ERM motors. The lowest part (up to 300Hz) of the audio signal is divided onto six frequency bands, 5-50Hz, 50-100Hz, 100-150Hz, 150-200Hz, 200-250Hz and 250-300Hz. The reason for using six frequency bands is so that each row of the 6×10 array can represent a single frequency band. Each row of 10 motors is split up in the middle into two rows of five motors with the left side representing the left channel of the stereo signal and the right side representing the right channel. The first audio-tactile mapping treats the motors in each row as an indicator of intensity, with the vibration moving closer to the middle depending on the magnitude of the frequency band. The second mapping also utilizes the same frequency bands but activates all the motors in each row at the same time.

Experimenting with different mappings will be crucial. Frequency scaling, from the frequencies perceptible by the ear (20-20kHz) to the the frequencies perceptible by the skin (5-1kHz) and melody extraction is also something to look at. This calls for a reliable hardware system where the experiments can be conducted.

3. THE IN-LAB EXPERIMENTATION RACK SYSTEM

The hardware system comprises of an audio interface that supports the Multichannel Audio Digital Interface (MADI) standard, digital/analogue (D/A) converters, custom made multi-channel low-power amplifiers and an actuator array (see figure 3), set up as an in-lab rack system.

3.1 Audio interface

The system uses the RME MADIface TX audio interface. MADI is a digital audio standard that supports bit transmission of up to 64 channels over a single fibre-optic cable. Since the MADIface TX has two MADI I/O optical ports, this setup allows for up to 128 channels of audio. For the purpose of this project only one port will be used, as a single MADI port will provide more than enough audio channels for the 6×10 tactile display.

A laptop personal computer (PC) connects to the audio interface via USB. A stereo signal from an audio source (which may be the PC itself or an external source) is fed

Figure 3. System flowchart. The in-lab rack system receives a stereo signal from an audio source and delivers 64 independent audio channels to a tactile display.

to the MADiface TX via two 6.3mm / 1/4" TRS connectors. Software on the PC then analyzes the signal, filters it via bandpass filters and routes it according to the selected mapping, to the outputs of the TotalMix FX digital real-time mixer included in the MADiface TX interface. Each output is thus assigned a selected pass-band.

3.2 Digital-to-analog conversion

The 64 channels of audio now need to be converted back to analog as digital audio will not affect the voice coils. The system uses two Ferrofish A32 A/D-D/A converters. The A32 has a MADI I/O port and 32 analog outputs via four Dsub25 / TASCAM connectors. By daisy chaining the two converters, TotalMix FX can route to both converters thus getting the full 64 channels of analog audio.

Each MADI I/O port induces slight latency (3 samples), which could cause the output signals of the two devices to be incoherent. The A32 offers the option of defining the device as primary or secondary in the setup menu. By setting the first A32 as primary and the second A32 as secondary, both devices will be in sync with the same delay. Further latency can be expected due to the D/A conversion process, depending on the sample rate (0.1625ms at 48kHz, 0.05625ms at 96kHz and 0.034375ms at 192kHz). Although the overall latency is minimal, it can be made up for by delaying the playback audio accordingly, if necessary.

Figure 4. Lofelt L5 actuator. When flat side is put up against the body it results in parallel vibration on the skin [11].

3.3 Amplification

To effectively drive the voice coil actuator (L5 from Lofelt GmbH, see section 3.4), the line-level signal needs roughly a 20dB gain. A custom made 32-channel low-power audio amplifier (E32) for this purpose is currently under development by the authors. The in-lab experimentation rack system incorporates two E32's. Each amplifier will receive audio signals from a Ferrofish A32 via four Dsub25 / TASCAM connectors and deliver amplified signals to the outputs via 32 RCA / phono plugs. Combined, the two E32's will thus deliver more than enough audio channels for the 6×10 array. The E32 is housed in a 2U 19" rack mount enclosure.

The E32 operates with the Texas Instruments TPA2025D1 integrated circuit (IC) amplifier. TPA2025D1 is a Class-D low-power audio amplifier IC that delivers 1.9W of power to an 8Ω load at a 3.6V supply (1% THD+N) and has a fixed gain of 20dB. With an efficiency of around 85%, heat dissipation is minimal which will be an advantage when implementing it to a wearable solution. It comes in a 1.53×1.98 mm space saving 12-ball BGA package (0.5mm pitch).

The TPA2025D1 has a built in battery tracking automatic gain control (AGC) which limits battery current consumption and extends the battery life. This will also be of benefit when implementing to a wearable solution. For the moment, however, the TPA2025D1 IC's will be powered by the E32's 3.6V / 2A power supply.

3.4 Actuators

L5 actuators (see figure 4) were chosen for the new tactile display. Designed by the Lofelt GmbH company, the L5 actuator is a voice coil packaged in a plastic case, 17×20.5 mm in length and width and 6.2mm in height. It can be driven by standard low-power audio amplifiers as an 8Ω load and has an acceleration response of a minimum of 0.5G for the frequency range of 35Hz to 1kHz. The L5 draws an average current of 57mA at maximum volume which means that the E32 will be able to supply enough current with all of its outputs in active mode.

By applying an audio signal to the voice coil, an alternating current (AC) runs through the winding, producing a magnetic field and interacting with a permanent magnet in the middle, pushing it either up or down (referring to figure 4). Every time the AC changes polarity the permanent magnet is pushed in the other direction, creating a vibration at the same frequency as the audio signal. Putting the L5's flat side up against the body will therefore result in a parallel vibration on the skin.

The ACUTE tactile display is estimated to contain 60 L5 actuators in an array of 6×10 like the SoV Tactile Belt used as frame of reference. However, experimentation will be conducted concerning the number of voice coils necessary for the full effect. In experimenting, various numbers of L5 coils are mounted on approximately 15cm thick layer of foam sponge which straps around the waist. A similar device (referred to as vibro-sponge) was used to measure relative vibrotactile spacial acuity in the SoV project [4,5]. Each L5 has an audio cable pair connected to it through pin sockets soldered to the coil wires and each pair has an RCA connector soldered to the other end. The cables form a tail with numbered RCA connectors that can be connected to the E32 amplifier outputs in a sequence befitting the vibro-sponge array.

By altering the software, adjusting the mapping and possibly changing the frequency bands and number of band-pass filters, many possible combinations of tactile feedback to represent music are available with the in-lab experimentation rack system. With a total of 64 independent channels, tactile stimulation can be presented to various body parts at once. For example, a 6×8 array could be placed on the torso while a strip of 8 coils can be placed on each arm.

4. CONCLUSION

We have presented the ACUTE Multi-CaTS proof-of-concept system, an in-lab rack mount solution for the purpose of evaluating different methods of audio-tactile mapping. The system will represent music using tactile stimulation to enhance the musical enjoyment of cochlear implant users. It will be used while experimenting with audio-tactile mapping as well as the number and placement of actuators. We will resume work, aiming towards a compact and wearable solution.

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